

PEDAGOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF SPIRITUAL-MORAL EDUCATION OF STUDENTS OF X-XI GRADES IN CLASSROOM HOURS

Salomov Gulom Yuldashevich

Teacher at Termiz State Pedagogical Institute

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Abstract. *In this article, the necessary conditions for the formation of spiritual and moral qualities in the students of X-XI classes of general education schools, the content of spiritual and moral education, and the role of the class leader in this process are consistently described.*

Keywords: *spiritual, moral, education, virtue, quality, class hour, class leader, national, value, spirituality, perspective, education, cultural, historical, tradition, custom, personality, citizenship, position.*

The stable economic development of any human society depends on the spiritual and moral level of its inhabitants. The issue of spiritual and moral education of students is stated in the educational documents of our country "Effective organizational and pedagogical based on the rich national, cultural and historical traditions, customs and universal values of the people in the spiritual and moral education of the young generation. Forms and tools will be developed and put into practice.

Formation of high spiritual and moral qualities in the mind of the young generation is a multifaceted and complex process. The spiritual and moral formation of students of X-XI classes of general education schools is inextricably linked with each other and requires regular and consistent implementation of comprehensive educational work. Only a clear and perfect system of educational influence, a holistic systematic approach ensures the effectiveness of spiritual and moral education. The existence of a perfect system in the educational process means not repeating the same work too much, preventing conflicting effects on the student, imposing the same requirements on the students and influencing them with integrity allows.

The process of spiritual and moral education is a set of consistent interactions between the teacher and the student aimed at achieving the effectiveness and quality of pedagogical activity, the correct level of education of the student's personality. Spiritual and moral education is a purposeful process of developing high consciousness, spiritual and moral qualities and behavior in students of general education schools in accordance with the ideas and principles of ethics. The main task of spiritual and moral education is to create a high spiritual and moral consciousness, stable behavior and moral qualities in students of general education schools that meet the requirements of the time, and to form an active life citizenship position of a person.

Taking into account our traditions, national values, conditions of the regions of our country, expanding its network and reforming it at the level of modern requirements is an urgent issue of today. Leaders of classes X-XI of general education schools in the course and extracurricular processes such qualities as friendship, solidarity, cooperation, mutual support, being a cure for someone else's pain are the basis of the strength of our people and nation, socio-economic, they should explain to their students that it is the basis of their political development.

Spiritual and moral education consists of forming spiritual consciousness, purposeful content, development of moral feelings, and formation of behavioral skills and habits. The purpose of spiritual and moral education it depends on the requirements of the society, and these requirements, in turn, the level of development of the productive forces and the work of teaching and educating students in the society is all about forming spiritual and moral qualities and faith in the young generation, making them loyal to the Motherland should serve to educate in spirit. Class leaders of general education schools play an important role in improving the moral and moral education of young people. In determining the goal of education, the requirements of the society, the spirit of the time, national characteristics, national customs, traditions, and customs are taken as a basis.

The purpose of education is to educate a fully matured, perfect human personality. Based on the goals of education, class leaders draw up a plan of educational work, determine its content, take into account the conditions of the school, choose different forms, methods, methods and means of educating students. The head of the class connects the education of students with life, allowing them to form their own faith and worldview.

When choosing educational methods, their compatibility with the level of team development is an important factor of success. Therefore, each class leader begins the class hours by determining the level of development of student group relations in the class. When class hours are organized in this way, students take an active part in the life of society, which helps to form the student's personality. It is necessary to inculcate the community spirit in students only when they are organized as a united team. One of the main tasks of the class leaders is to form a team of students, because the upbringing of the individual in the team is one of the leading principles of education.

Today, we are all worried about the fact that deviations are observed in the education of some young people, and that some of them are addicted to traditions and culture that are foreign to us. How can such young people contribute to the development of the Motherland in the future, what kind of staff will they become. The socio-economic, spiritual and moral development of our country at the level of the world's developed countries is largely aimed at the development of the young generation, a social activist who can freely enter into new social relations, recognizes universal human values, and is oriented towards spiritual and moral values. , depends on the development of highly cultured, qualified personnel.

No matter how much the spiritual values of foreign nations affect us, our national spiritual qualities such as respect for adults and parents, humility, honesty, faith, hard work, and hospitality are stable. Because these national values have been embedded in our blood since time immemorial. Traditions that are contrary to the moral values of our people about morality, attitude, shame, honesty and purity, and human dignity have a negative impact on the spirituality of young people. The future, prospects of our country, the success of the reforms in the field of education depend to a large extent on the teacher, his level, preparation, selflessness, enthusiasm for educating the young generation and raising them to the level of a mature person.

In all general education schools in our country, the educational process is organized and conducted directly by the head of the class. Achieving the educational goals in the new social conditions, organizing the educational activities of students in the classroom and outside the classroom, raising them to be educated, polite, religious, patriotic, hardworking, well-rounded

people and directing them to the profession. It is of particular importance as it is entrusted to the head of the class.

When determining the level of development of a group of students, the head of the class should not limit himself to the analysis of their relationships, which are manifested only in activities outside the classroom. The peculiarity of the head of the class is that he should form a team of students, not just a team of children. The main task of students is to study.

The most reliable way to determine the level of development of students in a class is to observe the level of active interaction with them in class, outside of class, and outside of school. The head of the class chooses educational methods depending on the level of development of the group of students. Prospects for the development of team relations in the educational process require great attention from the class leader.

There is a need for more interaction in team work. At any level of community development, the head of the class takes care of the formation of public opinion using certain methods. The head of the class is responsible for the education of the team and each student. Therefore, it is one of the unique features of the class hours to combine the team style and the individual form.

The fact that the spiritual and moral education of students is a priority task of state policy today, an important and urgent issue, increases the responsibility of class leaders of general education schools.

The happiness of every nation, the peace and happiness of the state depends on the education of the youth. A person changes physically and mentally during his life. Development is extremely strong during childhood, adolescence, and adolescence. During these years, the child matures as a person due to physical and mental growth and changes. As a result of the appropriate effect of education, the child matures as a member of society and takes a proper place in the system of complex social relations.

The success of education largely depends on taking into account the characteristics of the child's personality and the influence of the environment in which he lives. The child interacts with family members, educators, classmates, and people close to the family.

Forming high spiritual and moral qualities in the minds of students in the process of conducting classes for students of classes X-XI of general education schools, constantly keeping them informed about the latest achievements of science and culture, encouraging them with positive activities and educational activities booking is important.

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